

THE INFLUENCE OF THE MOLECULAR WEIGHT DISTRIBUTION OF NOVOLAC OLIGOMER ON THE CHAR RESIDUE OF THE CURED PHENOLIC FORMALDEHYDE RESIN

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SUMMARY

The phenolic resin had served as the binder for highly oxidation and ablative-resistant structures. The molecular structure and the molecular weight distribution of the novolac oligomer had great influence on the cross-linking structure and the char yield. In order to indicate the relation of the structure and the properties, in this paper, the molecular weight and its distribution were obtained through the field-desorption mass spectrometry(FD-MS) method, which could provide absolute molecular masses for each oligomeric species, from the ^{13}C -NMR spectrum, the novolac oligomer was detected to be composed of the ortho-ortho substituted structure, ortho-para substituted structure, para-para substituted structure. The chemical structures of the oligomer and their cured resins were also modeled. As ablative resistant materials, the favorable molecular structures of the novolac oligomer are containing mainly trimer, tetramer and pentamer.

Key words: novolac oligomer, phenolic resin, char residue, molecular weight distribution

INTRODUCTION

On account of the high yields of structural carbon char, the phenolic resin had played an important role in extensive military and commercial applications over the last 60 years, served as the binder for highly oxidation and chemical-resistant structures, such as rocket nozzles, ablative heat shields, refractories, fire protection shields, etc. Acid catalyzed condensation phenol-formaldehyde resin, known as novolac phenol-formaldehyde resin(NPFR), can be synthesized of various average molecular weight and molecular weight distribution according to its application. The molecular structure and the molecular weight distribution of the NPFR have great influence on the char residue and the ablative-resist performance of the products.

In the past researches, there was a conclusion that cured resin derived from high-ortho novolak had a lower heat-distortion temperature than the usual two-stage phenolics. This phenomenon was usually explained as resulting from reduced intermolecular hydrogen bonding between phenolic hydroxyls adjacent to the ortho-ortho methylene bridge tend to form hydrogen bonds intramolecularly, the thermal stability of cured two-stage phenolics was affected only by the molecular structure of the novolak and had no relation to degree of cross-linking, extent of curing, or residual amount of uncured novolak-i. e. , the lower the o-o-linked methylene-bridge content, the higher the thermal stability^[1].

For the general curing agent of NPFR was hexamethylenetetramine, which was certainly related to ammonia evolution, evolved the most volatiles. In general, the higher the gelation temperature of the binder, the more volatiles evolved, the higher the density of cross-linking, and the greater the thermal resistance^[2]. But the NPFR should flow with low viscosity at the beginning reactive temperature, and the reactive temperature of NPFR with hexamethylenetetramine began at about 100°C. the molecular weight couldn't be too much large so that the novolac easily flowing temperature was lower than the reaction temperature. and because the ability to melt-flow and penetrate fiber walls was strictly a function of molecular weight, the curing time of a resin depended not only upon the reactive groups, but also upon the resin's molecular-size distribution.

In order to study the molecular structure, the molecular weight and its distribution, coupling gel permeation chromatography(GPC) with low-angle laser light-scattering had been studied

extensively as a method for determining the MWD of phenolic resins^[3].

But in this study, the molecular weight and its distribution was obtained through the field-desorption mass spectrometry(FD-MS) method, which was a soft ionization technique developed by Karas and Hillenkamp and is now an established technique for the analysis of synthetic polymers, can provide absolute molecular masses for each oligomeric specie^[4], the method is much more direct or simpler than other traditional methods.

The structure of the novolac was detected by ¹³C -NMR, which have been used in studying phenolic resin since 1960s. M.G..Kim and his co-researcher had determined the carbon-13 NMR spectral data of various phenol-formaldehyde resin model compounds^[5]. For the NPFR mainly included -OH, -CH₂- , -C₆H₄ and -C₆H₃-, the ortho-ortho substituted structure, ortho-para substituted structure, para-para substituted structure could be measured by the chemical shift of -CH₂- groups.

In this research, We measured the molecular structure and the molecular weight distribution through precision instrument, on the other hand, measured the properties through traditional methods. A relation between the molecular conformation of the novolac oligomer and the ablative resistant property was set up after drawing the conclusion that only the novolac oligomer with the medium average molecular weight and narrower molecular weight distribution had the best char residue.

EXPERIMENT

Materials

Novolac oligomers: the NPFR with a varies of molecular weight distribution were prepared in laboratory.

Cured agent: hexamethylenetetramine was obtained commercially from the chemical reagent shop.

Test procedures and methods

Preparing the cured NPFR sample : the NPFR and hexamethylenetetramine were mixed fully, the weight ratio or NPFR to hexamethylenetetramine was equal to 100:12. the mixture was heated under 120°/0.5hour, 150°/ 1hour, 180°/ 3hours. Finally, the cured resin was grinded into powder.

The measurement of molecular weight distribution : the molecular weight distribution was measured by field-desorption mass spectrometry.

The measurement of substituted position of the phenol: which was measured by ¹³C-NMR in MeOH. The instrument was dmx400.

Static ablative test for measuring the char yield: about 3-5g cured resin powders were put in crucible, scorched in Muffle furnace under 850° for 10 minutes, then measured the char yield.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The NMR-13C spectrum and the NPFR structure

From the ¹³C-NMR spectrum (showed in figure1), the NPF was composed of the ortho-ortho substituted structure, whose chemical shift $\delta_1=30$, ortho-para substituted structure, whose chemical shift $\delta_2=34$, the para-para substituted structure, whose chemical shift $\delta_3=40$. the proportion of ortho-ortho structure to the ortho-para structure and para-para structure was about 1:2:1 according to the respectively integral area was 0.0390, 0.0742, 0.0353.

figure 1 ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of NPFR

The FD-MS spectrum and the molecular weight distribution

The NPFR prepared from different processing had different molecular weight distribution, in this paper they were divided into three groups on the bases of the molecular weight distribution. The first kind of NPFR with a broader molecular weight distribution was showed in figure 2, including mainly dimmers and large molecules.

figure 2 the molecular weight distribution of novolac oligomer including dimer mainly

The second kind was mainly concluded tetramer with narrower molecular weight distribution, was showed in figure 3

figure 3 the molecular weight distribution of novolac oligomer including tetramer mainly

The above two kinds of novolac oligomer had similar average molecular weight and melt viscosity under gel temperature, their macro- different couldn't be found out by ordinary method, such as viscosity and gel time.

The third novolac oligomer was showed in figure 4, which included much more large molecules and had much higher melt temperature .

figure 4 the molecular weight distribution of novolac oligomer including heptamer mainly

The molecular weight distribution and the char yield

The NPFR were put in three groups according to their main molecules were dimmers, tetramers or more than hexamer. The cured resin samples were grinded into powder, soched under 850 for 10 minutes. The char yields data were showed in table 1

Table 1 the char yield of three kinds of novolac resins

No.	Molecular weight distribution	Char yield (%)
1	Dimmer	57
2	Tetramer	59
3	Heptamer	54

From the static ablative test result, we drew a conclusion: the resin with tetramer had highest char yield, the resin with too much molecules of low molecular weight and of high molecular weight had lower char yield.

The molecular structure of oligomer and its influence on the flowing property and cross-linking structure

In order to explain the relation of static ablative test result and the molecular structure of the novolac oligomer and the cured resin, the three kinds of oligomer and their cured molecular structure were modeled as below.

The first kind novolac oligomer with mainly dimmer and broader molecular weight distribution

had good flowing property under the cured temperature because of the majority of dimer. But after the oligomers were cured, there were too many chain-ends and remaining active reaction positions, the favorable cross-linking structure couldn't be formed. The first molecular structures of NPFR and its cured resin were modeled in figure 5.

figure 5 the model structure of novolac oligomer and its cured resin with mainly dimer and broader molecular distribution

As to the second kind of NPFR, for the molecules had medium molecular weight, the molecular had bigger move ability to let the active react position draw close enough, in the same time, there were less chain-ends and remaining less active reaction positions, so a favorable cross-linking structure could form after the oligomer was cured by hexamethylenetetramine. The second molecular structures of novolac oligomer and its cured resin were modeled in figure 6.

figure 6 the model structure of novolac oligomer and its cured resin with mainly tetramer and narrower molecular distribution

As for the third kind structure of novolac oligomer, they were mainly composed of large molecules with long and tough molecular linkage, the tough molecules were short of enough flexibility, only parts of the active react position could draw close to form the crosslinked structure, while other parts of the active react positions were too apart from each other to form crosslinked structure. Consequently, there were also many interior defect in the cured structure when the NPF resin were reacted with hexamethylenetetramine. The third molecular structures of novolac oligomer and its cured resin were modeled in figure 7.

figure 7 the model structure of novolac oligomer and its cured resin with higher molecular weight

From the above char yield data and the molecular structure modeling, we could explain the relation of the static ablative test result and the phenolic resin molecular structure as follows :

Firstly, for the novolac oligomers were cured by hexamethylenetetramine, the beginning reactivetemperature was from 100 to 150, the melt temperature must be lower than the curing temperature, in the meantime, because the rigid phenolic structure lacked enough flexibility, if the molecules were too large, the molecules hadn't free movement ability to rearrange the active reaction position when the cured reaction was conducting between the active reaction groups. All those elements demanded the oligomer have lower average molecular weight to ensure the better mixing with hexamethylenetetramine and easy flowing when the resin was cured.

Secondly, in order to avoid a lot of chain-ends and remaining active positions occurred in the structure of the cured resin, the oligomer couldn't include too much free phenol or dimmer, especially when the concentration of the hexamethylenetetramine was relatively constant.

Finally, when the NPFR having narrower molecular weight distribution was composed of trimer, tetramer and pentamer, the cured resin would have perfect cross-linking structure, then the higher char yield would be obtained.

CONCLUSION

For the novolac oligomer have been playing a important part in extensive military and commercial applications as ablative resisting materials, it is necessary to study the relation of the char yield and the chemical structure of the novolac oligomer and the cured resin structure. In this paper, we showed the research result by measuring the molecular structure and the molecular weight distribution through modern apparatuses , measuring the char yields though the static ablative test. Finally, we concluded that the novolac oligomer of narrower molecular weight distribution , which included mainly trimer, tetramer and pentamer, had better melt flowing ability during the curing process and higher char yield.

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